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Three Properties of the Hepatitis C Virus RNA Genome Related to Antiviral Strategies Based on RNA-Therapeutics: Variability, Structural Conformation and tRNA Mimicry

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Abstract: The concept of using RNA molecules as therapeutic agents is receiving increasing attention by basic science and pharmaceutical research. Over the past five years, a number of clinical trials have been initiated to evaluate the efficacy and safety of several RNA agents for the treatment of a range of conditions from cancer to infectious disease. From a molecular biology perspective, two main factors are implicated in RNA therapeutics against pathogenic RNAs: i/ The activity, stability and delivery of the inactivating agent (ribozyme, RNase P, “decoy” RNA, aptamer, small interfering-RNA) and its co-localisation with the target; and ii/ The properties of the RNA substrate, which, in the case of an RNA virus, most likely limit the effectiveness of the inactivating agent. The main reasons are the limited size of the viral genome and the restrictions imposed by the RNA structure and variations at the target.

In the first section of this article we review three properties of the HCV RNA genome, from primary sequence to tertiary structure, which imply restrictions and opportunities for RNA-based treatment. In the second section, we briefly describe several of the RNA-based therapeutic strategies against HCV now under development.

Key Words: Hepatitis C virus, viral quasispecies, ribozymes, RNase P, siRNA, tRNA-like, RNA targeting.

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I. HEPATITIS C VIRUS RNA

It has been estimated that more than 200 million people worldwide are chronically infected with HCV. Hepatitis C virus is an enveloped virus classified in the family *Flaviridae* [1-4].

I.1. HCV Primary Sequence

I.1.a. *Linear Organisation of the Genome*

The HCV genome consists of a single, 9600 nt, unsegmented strand of RNA, with a plus polarity. The genome comprises a 5' untranslated region, which functions as an internal ribosome entry site (IRES), a long open reading frame extending along most of its length that encodes a polyprotein precursor of about 3010 amino acids, and a 3' untranslated region containing an internal poly U/polypyrimidine track [5, 6] (Fig. 1). Two RNA species are found in infected hepatocytes [7], a genomic RNA serving as mRNA for synthesis of the viral polyprotein and a minus-stranded RNA, from which polymerisation of the plus-stranded progeny is presumably initiated [3, 7]. Experiments using intrahepatic inoculation of *in vitro* transcripts of full-length HCV genome have proven that HCV RNA alone is sufficient to cause disease [8].

I.1.b. *Quasispecies Organisation of the HCV Genome*

Analysis of significant numbers of complementary DNA (cDNA) clones of the hepatitis C virus from single isolates when analysed in shorter time periods and within a given subgenomic region. This is especially evident in hypervariable region 1 (HVR1) of the E2 gene, the motif that displays the highest rate of mutation fixation of the viral genome [15]. Higher variation rates have been described during the acute phase [16] and in patients with ALT flare ups [17-19]. In addition, there seems to be a clear relationship between the rate of mutation fixation and the patient's immune status. In immunosuppressed patients - agammaglobulinemic [20, 21], with HIV-induced immunosuppression [22] or undergoing orthotopic liver transplantation [23, 24] - low rates of mutation fixation have been described.

Apart from the hypervariable motif, the E1, E2 and NS2 regions also present high evolutionary rates during the infection in a given patient, which may be more than five times greater than that of other coding regions such as the CORE and NS3.

Considering that mutations are introduced randomly, only a small number of mutants generated during the replication process occur in the HVR1 motif; most of them arise in the rest of the genomic sequence. Nonetheless, only a fraction of the latter are fixed to their carrying genomes as compared to the mutations generated in the HVR1 region. The dissimilar mutation fixation rates between HVR1 and other genomic loci, such as 5'UTR, CORE and NS3, reflect the fact that most variants are in constant extinction and are proofs of the competition among variants within the viral population, as has been extensively described for other RNA virus models [25]. The great capacity to adapt conferred by the competitive nature of the quasispecies structure is precisely what accelerates the evolution of a virus expanding under different influences

Genome Complexity

In most of the studies where sequencing has been used to analyse the genomic organisation of HCV, the complexity or the simultaneous presence of multiple variants has been observed even at the 5' untranslated region. Extreme genomic complexity values are found in HVR1 during chronic phases of the disease; examples have been described in which every analysed sequence is different (from ten to twenty independent clones) [26, 27]. During the infection, the complexity of HVR1, CORE and NS2 tends to increase as the disease stage progresses [18, 28-31].

Mutation Frequency

The mutation frequency measures the proportion of mutant residues in a population and is expressed as substitution per nucleotide. Among the genomes in the viral population present at a specific time point in a single patient, the frequency of mutation may vary from single mutations to more than 10% of the positions analysed [27, 32]. The complexity of HCV is very different depending on the locus analysed [9, 33, 34], the phase of infection [18, 28, 30, 35], the tissue under analysis [33, 32], the immunological status of the patient [22, 34, 36] and whether the patient is under treatment [37-39]. Additionally, viral load may have a considerable effect on the sequence space that a virus can occupy [40]. All these situations have been, and still are, subject to experimental investigation.

In summary, complexity and mutant frequency are dynamic features of the HCV quasispecies that change sequentially during the course of infection as a result of random accumulation of mutations, subsequent shaping by random events and by positive and negative selective pressures operating in the infected host. Analyses of HCV quasispecies have been reported in acute and chronic infection [18, 28, 30, 35, 41], in interferon-treated patients [18, 42, 43], in donor-

recipient [26, 44, 45] and in mother-baby pairs [46, 47]. HCV quasispecies have also been studied in a variety of biological samples including serum, peripheral blood mono- nuclear cells and liver specimens [32, 48], as well as various fragments of the same liver (positive- and negative-strand populations) [33].

1.1.c HCV Genotypes

The long-term evolutionary consequence of the accumulation and fixation of mutations is the generation of genetically differentiated groups or genotypes [12, 49, 50]. Many studies have brought together the sequences obtained in different geographic areas and grouped them according to their genotype and subtype homology. In the currently used classification system, HCV genotypes correspond to the six main branches of a phylogenetic tree and a large number of subtypes correspond to more closely related sequences within five of the six main genotypes [51-53]. Genotypes are numbered from 1 to 6 and subtypes designated as a, b, c, etc., in both cases in order of discovery. Thus, the sequence of the original prototype cloned by Houghton *et al.* was assigned genotype 1a, the Japanese HCV-J and -BK were assigned genotype 1b and so on.

The six main HCV genotypes show equal divergence among each other differing by 31% to 43% of nucleotide positions according to a pairwise comparison of the complete genomic sequences (corresponding to approximately 30% divergence in amino acid sequences). The final subtype grouping within each genotype is quite uniform, with 20- 23% divergence among subtypes.

Geographical Distribution of HCV Genotypes

Some HCV genotypes such as 1a, 2a and 2b are widely distributed throughout the world, whereas others such as 5a and 6a are confined to specific geographic areas. Genotype 1b is more common in Southern and Eastern Europe than in Northern Europe or the United States. There is a drastic difference in genotype distribution between Southeast Europe and Turkey (where the most common genotype is 1b) and countries of the Middle East and Northern and Central Africa [54, 55]. Genotype 4 is predominant in these areas, with a high frequency of HCV infection in Egypt (20-30% of the population) mainly due to subtype 4a [56, 57]. Genotype 5a is often found in South Africa among blood donors chronically infected by HCV. In the west of Africa the predominant genotypes are 1 and 2, with a wide diversity of subtypes [58-60].

In Japan, Taiwan and some parts of China, 1b, 2a and 2b are common genotypes. The genotype with the most restricted geographic distribution is 6a, originally reported in Hong Kong, where approximately one third of blood donors infected with HCV have this genotype. Other genotypes found in Vietnam [61], Thailand [61-63] and Indonesia [64] are grouped together as subtypes of genotypes 3 or 6, although they were originally reported as independent genotypes (from 7 to 11).

1.2. HCV RNA Secondary Structure

Genomic RNA sequences determine secondary structures that are part of the viral phenotype. RNA secondary structures are generated by two or more consecutive Watson- Crick base-pairings, which can involve distant bases in the RNA molecule.

1.2.a. 5' untranslated Region

The secondary structure of the 5'UTR of HCV has been extensively studied. Biochemical and functional studies have revealed that the HCV 5'UTR folds into a highly ordered complex structure with multiple stem-loops [65-68] containing two distinct RNA elements, a short 5' proximal RNA element (nucleotides 1-43) that regulates HCV RNA replication and translation [69-71] and a longer internal ribosome entry site (IRES) element (for IRESes structure-function relationship, see E.Martínez-Salas and O.Fernández-Miragall in this issue), consisting of nucleotides 44 to a region surrounding position 370 and forming domains II, III and IV (Fig. 3). Mutational analysis has revealed that maintenance of the structural element is critical for internal initiation of cap-independent translation of the viral polyprotein [72]. Domains II and III of the 5'UTR are both essential for IRES activity, while conservation of the sequence downstream of the initiator AUG (domain IV) is required for optimal IRES- directed translation [73-76]. Comparison of HCV 5'UTR sequences from infected individuals has revealed that variations are limited to particular sites [49, 77]. The sites of genotype-specific variability are covariant substitution sites and they maintain the base pairing required for the 5'UTR secondary structure model [78]. Efforts to correlate IRES conformation from different HCV genotypes and their respective translation efficiencies, with different response to IFN-treatment have been unsuccessful [79, 80]. Phylogenetic sequence alignments of pestivirus and flavivirus have suggested that the deduced domain II structure is conserved within the IRES. Despite marked differences in the primary nucleotide sequence within conserved helical segments, the sequences of the intervening single stranded loop segments are highly conserved in these different viruses [81]. Finally, in an extensive comparison between flavivirus and picornavirus IRES elements by negative transmission electron microscopy, it was concluded that all the examined flavivirus IRESes folded to give a structure similar to HCV IRES. In contrast, the larger picornavirus IRESes were morphologically similar to each other, but different from those of flavivirus [82].

I.2.b. 3' untranslated Region

The RNA genome of HCV terminates with a 98-base sequence having a putative secondary structure that is highly conserved in all genotypes [83]. Enzymatic and chemical approaches have yielded data consistent with a stem-loop structure within the 3'-terminal 46 bases while the 5' 52 nucleotides of this 98-base element appear to be less ordered and may exist in multiple conformations [84-86]. This region is required for *in vivo* infectivity [87] and serves as a cis-acting element in HCV RNA replication, as evidenced by its interaction with many cellular proteins [88-93] and most important, with human ribosomal proteins [94]. Moreover, mutational analysis of the 3' terminal hairpin of subgenomic HCV RNAs replicating in human hepatoma cells has conclusively demonstrated its role in viral RNA replication [95]. Interestingly, a recent study combining chemical and enzymatic probing with computer prediction has shown that the 3' end of negative (-) strand RNA does not fold into a mirror image, even though it has the antisense sequence of the 5' (+) UTR. Comparison of the replication initiation sites on the two strands reveals common structural features that may play key functions in the replication process [96].

I.3. HCV RNA Tertiary Structure

Tertiary structures are formed by the interaction of secondary structure elements (folded groups of stems, loops and single-stranded regions) and by the interaction of secondary structure elements and single-stranded regions. In addition, local tertiary structure elements (intra-stranded non-Watson-Crick bonding) may contribute to the final folding [97].

I.3.a. Within the IRES

The IRES contains most of the tertiary structure elements described so far in HCV RNA. As shown by mutation and deletion analyses, proper folding of most of the domains is essential for interactions with host factors, particularly with components of the host translation apparatus [98-100].

The first independent structural element to be described in HCV IRES is a pseudoknot located upstream of the initiator AUG [72]. Pseudoknots consist of a "double" stem-loop structure in which bases outside of a first stem-loop are paired with those in the loop so as to form a second stem. When the second stem is stacked upon the first one, the structure reconstitutes a quasi-continuous mini-helix [101]. Pseudoknot structures are often recognised by components of the translation apparatus. In the case of HCV RNA, genetic, biochemical and thermodynamic analyses have provided evidence of the formation of a pseudoknot implicating bases 126-134 paired to bases 315-323 (stem I) and bases 305-311 paired to bases 325-331 (stem II). This pseudoknot has been shown to be necessary for efficient initiation of translation.

An element of local tertiary structure was recently identified in domain II of the HCV IRES [102]. In a RNA-RNA UV-crosslinking experiment, it was found that two non-contiguous regions of the IRES (bases 53-68 and 103-117) contact to form this tertiary structure element, which may be implicated in protein binding. Long-range RNA-RNA interactions were subsequently described inside the IRES in a study using non-denaturing gel electrophoresis [103]. The authors demonstrated that domain II is also able to interact with domain IV, located at the end of the IRES (3' boundary).

In the same study, other RNA-RNA interactions were detected between domain II and IIIabcd through the hairpin IIIId and between stem-loop IIIef and domain IV, probably participating in the pseudoknot structure.

Evidence that HCV IRES has a generally stable tertiary structure, has been provided by chemical and enzymatic studies using HCV IRES RNA in solution. The IRES adopts a unique conformation at physiological salt concentrations and in the absence of any additional factor predicted to interact with it [98]. This structure is cation-dependent (magnesium), is not globular (extended structure with some flexibility) and contains two independent folded domains. The first domain comprises the four-way junction IIIabc and the other contains stem-loop IIIId, loops IIIe and IIIf and the pseudoknot described above. Various studies have indicated the importance of proper folding of domain IIIId for IRES function [104, 105]. Dependence on magnesium for the folding of domain IIIabc has been confirmed recently by another study that also revealed a dynamic equilibrium between two antiparallel and parallel conformations of domain IIIabc in solution [106].

I.3.b. Other Parts of the Genome

To date, few tertiary structure domains have been described outside the IRES. The presence of two transfer-RNA (tRNA)-like domains in HCV RNA has been proposed recently [107] (see mimicry section in this review). Although no definitive function has been assigned to any of the tRNA-like structures as yet, it is of interest that they both lie at junction sites in the HCV genome (coding/ non coding region and structural/ non-structural protein coding sequences). It has been suggested that the CORE coding sequence contains a pseudoknot structure (bases 392-508) that could participate in the translational frameshift event leading to expression of the F protein and a short 1.5 kD peptide [108].

I.3.c. Long-Range RNA-RNA Interactions

It has quickly become evident that the CORE coding sequence plays a greater role in IRES function than the CORE protein [109] and that this interaction probably implies direct long-range RNA-RNA interactions [110]. Kim *et al.* have proposed a model of RNA-RNA interaction between bases 428-442 of the CORE coding sequence and 24-38 of the IRES that could down-regulate HCV IRES-dependent translation *in vitro* and *in vivo* [111]. Such a structure

could be an alternative to the pseudoknot structure proposed by Choi *et al.* [108].

I.3.d. Mimicry

The ability of viral systems to mimic tRNA, as has been recently found in HCV RNA, was first discovered 30 years ago at the 3' -ends of the turnip yellow mosaic virus (TYMV) and tobacco mosaic virus (TMV), which were found to undergo covalent linkage with amino acids catalysed by aminoacyl-tRNA-synthetases reviewed in [112]. Subsequently, these and other plant viral RNAs were seen to be accessible to a battery of factors involved in other tRNA-related activities [112-115], including bacterial RNase P [116], CTP, ATP: tRNA nucleotidyl transferase and elongation factor EF-TU [117, 118] (Table 1). *In vivo* functional mimicry has been recently demonstrated to be complete, at least in TYMV, since viral RNAs were amino acid donors for protein synthesis [119].

RNase P from HeLa cells specifically and effectively cleaves hepatitis C virus transcripts *in vitro* at two sites, one near the AUG start triplet following domain IV of the HCV IRES between bases 360-362 and one within an internalgenomic region (A2860) [107]. RNase P specifically cleaves pre-tRNA in all organisms to produce mature 5' ends. RNase P cleavage has also reliably identified a number of authenticated tRNA-like domains in non-tRNA molecules, including bacterial signal recognition particle (SRP) and transfer-messenger RNAs (tmRNAs) and various plant viral RNA genomes [116, 120-123] (Table 1). Additionally, HCV RNA competitively inhibits pre-tRNA cleavage by RNase P, suggesting that HCV has structural characteristics similar to tRNA [107].

Despite the notorious heterogeneity and dynamics of change of the HCV genome, the conservation of RNase P-cleavable structures in variant genomes reveals their importance for virus viability [107].

No evidence of subgenomic RNAs have been reported [124], arguing against an active role of RNase P cleavage in HCV biology. Mimicry of tRNA's shape probably works as an entrance pass to the ribosome A site in plant viruses [119, 125]. The presence of a pseudoknot near the HCV IRES cleavage site, which is a property of most plant RNA viruses, increases the similarities between the two systems. Such structures may contribute to the recruitment of the trans- lational machinery in the absence of a 5' terminal cap. In fact, the pseudoknot domain of HCV IRES is among those protected from extensive pancreatic RNase A digestion by initiating 80 S ribosomes [126].

Lyons and Robertson have analysed the IRES domains of several viral RNA genomes including two pestiviruses related to HCV (classical swine fever virus and bovine viral diarrhoea virus) and two unrelated viruses (encephalomyo- carditis virus and cricket paralysis virus) and have found similarly placed RNase P cleavage sites in the IRESes [127]. The authors suggested that tRNA-like domains might be general structural features of virus IRESes and that such tRNA features could be recognised by pre-existing ribosomal tRNA-binding sites as part of the IRES initiation cycle.

II. TARGETING

II.1. The Problem of Accessibility

The general principle underlying RNA therapeutics is efficient annealing of complementary sequences of the RNA compound to viral RNA [128-131]. However, the higher- order structure of the viral RNA molecule may interfere with association of the RNA agent. First, intramolecular base pairing within viral RNA could preclude base pairing between the RNA agent and the cleavage site. Second, the tertiary structure of large RNA molecules may inhibit RNA agent association by steric hindrance. In the living cell, passing ribosomes and proteins that bind to viral RNA may also contribute to problems in agent-target formation [130- 134].

The discovery of accessible sites for hybridisation of the RNA agent requires the identification of unstructured and exposed sites in cellular RNA. This is accomplished by a combination of computational methods, cell-free mRNA assays, *in vitro* targeting in the presence of cellular extracts or/and direct mapping of the RNA substrate in living cells.

An RNA strand can form a large number of possible Watson-Crick base conformations. The lowest free energy secondary structure can be calculated, but computational prediction of the secondary structure for large RNA molecules is a difficult task and the result is a gross approximation of RNA accessibility that does not take into account the tertiary structure and protein-RNA interactions. Nevertheless, basic studies over the last several years [135-137] have led to the development of software tools and www services that allow searching for structural patterns on RNA sequences (mfold programme: <http://bioinfo.math.rpi.edu/zukerm/rna/>; the Vienna RNA package <http://www.tbi.univie.ac.at/ivo/RNA>). Other advances have allowed the prediction of "untypical" (non-A) RNA conformation [138], conformational switches [139] and detection of conserved and single-stranded [140] elements in complete viral genomes [141]. Computational target screening may increase the probability of successful selection of RNA agents that are effective in cells. As proposed by Scherr *et al.* [128] this approach can be used in a two-step procedure for predicting accessibility: first, computer-aided selection of accessible sites and then, confirmation by experimental procedure.

Both enzymatic and chemical methods are available to obtain information about the secondary structure of RNA molecules. A large battery of nucleases exists, with varying specificity for single-stranded or double-stranded regions. Their combined use with chemical methods can provide a checking system and complementary information [142]. Nevertheless, the relationship between accessibility and structure may be complex even in well-characterised RNA structures.

The use of RNase H mapping allows direct empirical testing of accessible sites in the RNA substrate and provides more information than approaches involving other ribonucleases or chemical agents. The accessible substrate region hybridises with a complementary DNA oligonucleotide, whereas nucleotides sequestered in secondary or tertiary structures are inaccessible for hybridisation. The hybridised regions are subsequently identified in gel electrophoresis after RNase H treatment, which degrades RNA in the RNA-DNA duplexes. The technique uses oligonucleotide “walks”, spacing oligonucleotides of a given length at intervals along the RNA and choosing the ones with greatest activity [143- 146].

Combinatorial screening using libraries of random [143] or semi-random [147] DNA oligonucleotides followed by RNase H treatment have been used to identify ribozyme-accessible sites. This approach provides a cost-effective mapping technique and speeds up the process.

A method to map the degree of structure of large regions of the HCV genome has been developed recently using DNA microarray technology [148]. The method consists of hybridisation of HCV RNA transcripts with complementary oligonucleotides printed on a solid support and representing regions having different structural degrees [133]. This approach is able to distinguish regions with dissimilar structural degrees, allowing its application to the systematic analysis of complete genome regions in different genotypes. Preliminary data reveal a quite considerable degree of structure distributed unevenly along the entire HCV RNA genome [148].

It is important to determine whether *in vitro* approaches for predicting accessible sites in viral RNA are realistic *in vivo*. There are few comparative analyses of the secondary structure of a synthetic RNA and the same intracellular RNA, but available findings support the idea that the structures are similar [149] although a percentage of nucleotides show different sensitivity patterns. Conclusions from several studies (reviewed by [143]) have suggested a correlation between RNA oligonucleotide binding to folded RNA structure *in vitro* and its biological activity [150]. This has also been found for ribozymes [151-153] and RNAi [154]. Targeting experiments in cell extracts developed to create a protein environment that can influence the RNA structure is a good parallel to direct mapping of substrate RNA with dimethylsulfate in cells [155].

II.2. The Problem of Variability

Watson-Crick and more complex tertiary interactions are responsible for the highly specific recognition of viral RNA by therapeutic agents. As explained in the previous section (I-1-b) the viral RNA genome has a highly sequence variability. This quality turns into a slippery target for a technique that is strictly sequence dependent. Results from studies with different RNA agents suggest that these agents may tolerate some mismatches in their substrate recognition domains but not others, and that too many mismatched positions may totally abrogate their activity [156-158]. Phylogenetic analysis involving the complete viral sequence across a number of viral isolates and viral genotypes is useful for detecting conserved motifs in multiple alignments and may be able to define adequate targets. The 5' and 3' UTRs are assumed to be the optimal regions. Nevertheless, this argument does not invalidate the examination of other less highly conserved regions for targeting purposes. In each case, the extent of sequence variation may not correlate with the relative ability to escape attack with RNA agents.

The complex behaviour of RNA virus quasispecies in response to selective factors makes such direct correlations difficult. Although there are no reports on virus resistance to RNA agents *in vivo* or in cultured cells, examples of fitness recovery in debilitated viruses show that even mutants thought to be improbable may arise [159, 160].

The accumulated experience from studies on interferon (IFN) treatment in HCV infection may be representative of the potency of HCV variation in evading antiviral treatment *in vivo*.

For some time, it has been observed that patients with recent infection generally respond favourably to interferon, whereas those with chronic or long-standing infection respond badly or not at all. This is consistent with the concept that chronic infections accumulate considerable heterogeneity, making them more difficult to combat. Molecular studies have shown that there is a relationship between the degree of heterogeneity of the HVR-1 region of HCV and response to IFN treatment [18, 161-163]. Moreover, in patients who respond to treatment, either at short-term or definitively, the number of variants and the degree of heterogeneity of the sequences decreases during treatment [37, 164-166]. Pawlotsky *et al.* [167] performed an extensive study of the sequences that make up the NS5A quasispecies of HCV genotype 1b in different patients, as well as their evolution before and after treatment. The authors concluded that, as occurs in the hypervariable region, there is an inverse correlation between the complexity of the quasispecies in NS5A and the response to interferon, i.e. treatment-resistant 1b genotypes present more complex quasispecies. It is probable, however, that this phenomenon has a quite intricate basis, with other regions of the viral genome besides NS5A contributing to the resistance to treatment.

The most likely conclusion derived from these findings is that the level of RNA variation arising during HCV infection will require multiple targeting by RNA-based therapies.

II. 3. An opportunity: tRNA mimicry in HCV RNA

The strong tendency to maintain RNase P sensitive structures within HCV RNA virus genome might be important for the development of therapeutic strategies against the virus, since these structures could be highly susceptible targets for bacterial RNase P ribozymes [168, 107]. Moreover, recognition of structures instead of sequences may represent a great advantage in the fight against variable viruses, because single or even double mutations in the target

might not disrupt the cleavable tRNA-like structure (at least in the human RNase P enzyme model) [158]. Additionally, it is known that some forms of the catalytic RNA moiety from *E. coli* RNase P, M1 RNA (either specifically modified or *in vitro* selected) can be introduced into mammalian cells for the purpose of carrying out targeted cleavage of mRNA molecules (Table 2).

Work in progress in our laboratory has revealed that the *E. coli* enzyme, M1 RNA is unable to cleave tRNA mimics at either of the two sites *in vitro* (Sabariegos *et al.* in preparation). M1 catalytic activity is highly dependent on the presence of a 3' CCA terminus on the substrate, a sequence motif that is not present in HCV tRNA-like positions [169, 170]. In contrast, the ribozyme for the cyanobacterium *Synechocystis. sp.*, which does not present such dependence [171], effectively cleaves HCV RNA, at least in the tRNA-like domain of the IRES. This fact, besides being independent proof of the similarity between HCV structures and tRNA, opens the doors to an unexpected therapeutic strategy (Sabariegos *et al.* in preparation).

III. RNA AGENTS

III.1. Ribozymes

The fact that RNA has catalytic ability was elucidated in the early 1980's when Thomas Cech and Sidney Altman independently discovered the first catalytic RNA molecules: the self-splicing group I intron of *Tetrahymena* and the RNA component of RNase P [172, 173]. RNA molecules with catalytic activity were called ribozymes and since their discovery, RNA catalysts have been described in several essential cellular reactions such as RNA splicing and RNA cleavage [174-177] (Table 3).

Ribozymes can act as enzymes, catalyzing biochemical reactions— in the complete absence of protein cofactors. Most naturally-occurring ribozymes catalyze the cleavage or ligation of RNA phosphodiester bonds [178-180] through two catalytic mechanisms, transesterification and hydrolysis. These ribozymes catalyze in a sequence-specific manner (except RNase P, which recognises structural features) and show high affinity for their substrates. Specificity is determined by Watson-Crick base-pairing between the ribozyme and its substrate molecules, particularly nucleotides near the cleavage site (critical nucleotides). Ribozymes contain two distinct motifs: catalytic and substrate binding domains.

Most catalytic RNAs, with the exception of RNase P, are intramolecular *cis*-acting ribozymes by nature [173, 178, 181, 182]; therefore, they are modified during the reaction. For therapeutic purposes, the catalytic center of these naturally self-cleaving ribozymes is engineered to target specific sequences in *trans* in order to develop agents that catalyze intermolecular reactions to cleave exogenous substrate molecules [178, 183-186] (Table 2).

The capacity of ribozymes to specifically inactivate other RNAs makes them potentially valuable tools for gene therapy. In addition to naturally occurring ribozymes, novel catalytic motifs (therapeutic ribozymes) have been developed as therapeutic agents to inhibit viral replication, modulate tumour progression, and analyse cellular gene function.

III. 2. RNA Interference

RNA interference (RNAi), a biological process of post-transcriptional gene silencing, first discovered in *Caenorhabditis elegans*, occurs in most living organisms, from plants to mammals [187, 188]. This process is mediated by double-stranded RNAs, 21-nt long, known as small-interfering RNA (siRNA), which have sequences homologous to the silenced RNAs [189-191]. Small interfering RNAs are produced from double-stranded RNA by the DICER enzyme, a member of the RNase III family and are captured by a protein complex called RISC— whose exact composition remains partially unknown. The siRNA are used by RISC to recognise and cleave the mRNA target in a sequence-dependent process.

The natural functions of RNAi, which have not as yet been completely defined, include the regulation of endogenous genes, antiviral defense and response to transposons; thus this system may play a role in "intracellular immunisation" [192]. RNAi is a powerful tool for studies on genetic function, commanding the knock-down of a specific gene without destruction or mutation of the genetic material. It can also help in the development of specific new genetic therapies [193]. Several articles have reported the successful use of siRNAs as antiviral therapy and recent reports have shown that the HCV replicon is eliminated by RNAi in a human hepatoma cell line (Huh-7) and in a mouse model (Table 4). The liver seems to be particularly receptive to exogenous RNA [194]. Nevertheless better delivery methods, such as formulation of siRNAs with compounds that promote transit across cell membranes, are clearly required before siRNAs can be used in therapy [195]. Combinations of RNAi with antisense RNAs, and ribozymes, may comprise an effective RNA cocktail for therapy against HCV and other viruses.

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TABLES

Table 1. Recognition of tRNA Elements by tRNA Modifying Enzymes

RNA element	Reference	Aa-tRNA synthetase	CTP -ATP nucleotidyl transferase	Eftu/EF1	RNase P		Cloverleaf structure
					<i>E. coli</i>	Mammalian	
TYMV	[112, 114, 116]	Val 3' 82 nt	D/T loop 75 nt	Accepto _r Aa (47 nt)	Min. 3' (23 nt) Opt. 3' (100 nt)		
TMV	[114]	His 3' 95 nt	55 nt	Yes	No		
BMV	[114]	Tyr	Yes	Yes	No		
HCV	[107]	-	-	-	No	Yes	
Pestiviruses	[127]	-	-	-		Yes	
Coliphages	[114]	No	Yes	Yes	Yes		
Operon hisE (<i>E. coli</i>)	[114]	-	-	-	-		
Gen Thr (<i>E. coli</i>)	[114, 196-198]	Thr	-	-	-		
Group 1 Intron	[114, 199, 200]	TyrRS					
	[114, 201, 202]	LeuRS					
Mitochondrial DNA (D-displacement loop)	[114, 203, 204]	-			Yes		Yes

Table 2. Ribozymes and Clinical Applications

Virus	Ribozyme	Target	Ribozyme efficiency
HCV	Hammerhead	5' NCR region	90% inhibition of replication (HCV-PV chimera) [205]
		5'NCR region (-)RNA	Elimination of RNA [206]
	Hammerhead (nuclease-resistant) + Interferon	5' NCR region	>98% inhibition of HCV-PV replication, combined with low doses of IFN [207]
		5' NCR region	Clinical trial (Phase I) [205, 208]
	Hairpin	5' NCR region	Reduction of 79% in the retroviral particles level [209]
		Core	Reduction of 94% in the retroviral particles level [209]
	Human RNase P	5' NCR	<i>In vitro</i> [107]
		NS2 region	<i>In vitro</i> [107]
	<i>E. coli</i> RNase P (M1RNA)	NS2 region	<i>In vitro</i> [146]
HBV	Hammerhead	HBx mRNA	Reduction in protein level and virus-associated diseases, antireplicative effect [210, 211]
	Hairpin	X protein mRNA	80% inhibition of infection [212]
		Polymerase mRNA	80% inhibition of infection [212]
		Pregenomic RNA	Inhibition of viral replication [153]
	Hairpin (nuclease-resistant)	Surface antigen mRNA	Reduction of antigen level [213]
		Pregenomic RNA	Block the life cycle of HBV [213]
	Human RNase P	Surface antigen mRNA	<i>In vitro</i> [214]
HIV-1	Hammerhead	<i>Tat</i> mRNA	>80% inhibition of replication [215, 216, 217]
		<i>Env</i> mRNA (multitarget)	Significant reduction of mRNA; could potentially be effective against several isolates [218]
		<i>Gag</i> mRNA	Significant reduction of mRNA, reflecting reduction in antigen p24 levels [219]
		<i>Pol</i> mRNA	Suppression of viral activity [220]
		5' LTR region	Reduction of HIV activity [221, 222]
	Hairpin	5' LTR region	Reduction of HIV activity [221]. Inhibition of 95% in HIV activity, relation between ribozyme expression level and selective advantage [223]
		<i>Rev / env</i> mRNA	Inhibition of replication evidences that one point mutation near the cleavage site affects the inhibition level [224]
	Hairpin	<i>Pol</i> mRNA	Significant inhibition of

			replication depending on the strains [225]
		5' LTR region	Clinical trial (Phase I) [226]
		<i>Pol</i> mRNA	Clinical trial (Phase I) [226]
	Human RNase P	5' LTR region	Inhibition of replication and virus associated-cytopathology [227]
Influenza	Hairpin	5' end of mRNAs	70-80% of resistance [228]
	Human RNase P	Polymerase (<i>PB2</i>) and nucleocapsid (<i>NP</i>) mRNAs	Complete inhibition targeting the 2 mRNAs simultaneously [229]
HSV-1	Human RNase P	Thymidine kinase mRNA	80% reduction in the mRNA and protein expression level [230]
	<i>E. coli</i> RNase P (M1 RNA)	Thymidine kinase mRNA	80% reduction in the mRNA and protein expression level [231]
HSV-1		ICP4 transcription activator mRNA	80% reduction in the activator level and 1000-fold in viral growth [232]
	<i>E. coli</i> RNase P (M1 RNA)	Thymidine kinase mRNA	90-95% reduction in the mRNA and protein expression level [233]
HCMV	<i>E. coli</i> RNase P (M1 RNA)	IE1 / IE2 mRNAs	90-95% reduction in the protein expression level 150-fold in viral growth [234, 235]
Papilloma (HPV-16)	Hairpin	HPV-16 E6 /E7 mRNA	Inhibition of HPV-16 E6 / E7; immortalization [236]
Mumps	Hairpin Hammerhead	Nucleocapsid mRNA	Reduction in mRNA level and progeny [237]

Table 3. Ribozyme Activity in Nature and Therapy

Ribozyme	Site (nt)	Biological source	Catalytic activity	Role in nature	Therapeutic applications
Hammerhead	31-42	Plant viroids, satellite RNAs and newt satellite DNA	Sequence specific ribonuclease	Self-cleaving RNA	Digestion of viral, oncogene or mutant RNA
Hairpin	50 (minimum sequence)	Plant viroids and satellite RNAs	Sequence specific ribonuclease	Self-cleaving RNA	Digestion of viral, oncogene or mutant RNA
RNase P	350-410 (bacteria) 344 (human)	All cells and organelles that synthesize tRNA	Structure specific ribonuclease	Pre-tRNA processing	Digestion of viral RNA
Group I intron	413 (<i>Tetrahymena thermophila</i>)	Eukaryotes, prokaryotes, bacteriophages	RNA cleavage and ligation	Splicing	Repair of mutant mRNA or oncogenes
Group II intron	887 (yeast mitochondria)	Eukaryotic organelles, prokaryotes	RNA and DNA cleavage and ligation	Splicing and transposition	DNA repair
VS ribozyme	154	<i>Neurospora</i> mitochondria	RNA cleavage and ligation	Self-cleaving RNA	Proposed to digest structured RNA substrates
Hepatitis Delta virus (HDV)	85 (required)	HDV	RNA cleavage	Self-cleaving RNA	RNA repair
Spliceosome (U2+U6 snRNAs)	180, 100	Eukaryotes	RNA cleavage and ligation	Splicing	Repair of mutant mRNA
Ribosome (23S rRNA)	2600	Eukaryotes, prokaryotes	Peptidyl transfer	Synthesis of sequence-specific peptide bonds	

Table 4. RNAi Against HCV RNA

HCV Target	Delivery of target/siRNAs	Results	Observations
5' UTR luciferase-replicon	Transfection of Huh-7 cells	80% decrease in replication [238]	First siRNAs silencing in replicon systems
5' UTR replicon	Transfection of Huh-7 cells	- 80-fold decrease in HCV RNA - >98% inhibition of NS5A expression [239]	Possibility of host gene knock-down in an HCV replicon containing cell line
NS3 and NS5B replicon	Transfection of Huh-7 cells	siRNA antiviral effect is independent of IFN and cell cycle [240]	
NS3 and NS5B replicon	Transfection of Huh-7 cells: - naked siRNAs - DNA template (bicistronic vector)	Silencing observed: - Replicon infected cells (> 72 hours) - 3 weeks using siRNAs expressed from DNA templates [241]	
- 5' UTR IRES-luciferase construct - 5' UTR replicon	Transfection of Huh-7 cells: - naked siRNAs - DNA template	80% suppression in luciferase activity using lower siRNA concentration (2.5 nM) [242]	Determination of siRNA efficiency depending on the position in the target
NS5B-luciferase construct	Hydrodynamic transfection of siRNAs in livers of adult mice	75% reduction of NS5B expression [243]	First demonstration of inhibition in an animal model

FIGURES

Figure 1

Fig. (1). Organization of the hepatitis C virus genome and its encoded polyprotein. The relative locations of the 5' untranslated region (5'UTR), the structural genes including the core (C) and envelope genes 1 and 2 (E1 and E2), the p7 coding region, the non-structural genes NS2 to NS5 and the 3' untranslated region (3'UTR) are shown as proposed for several HCV isolates.

Figure 2

Fig. (2). Schematic representation of a viral quasispecies. From an original defined sequence, each round of replication lead to the appearance of variant genomes. Symbolic viral particles are drawn on the right part of the figure. Each line represents a viral genome and symbols correspond to point mutations.

